

How did human curiosity guide a citizen science project that monitors banded birds? Lessons for future projects in Brazil

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English version by River Warbler Ahlquist¹ and Eduardo R. Alexandrino²

1 - Undergraduate student, Cornell University. Granted by – Experimental Learning Award – summer 2024.

2 - Post-doctoral fellow, Cornell Lab of Ornithology (Cornell University, USA).

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Abstract

Conducting scientific research with public participation can close the gap between academia and society, however, this can be a complex task. In this manuscript, we share our experiences from four ornithological studies carried out as part of the citizen science project “Did I see a banded bird!?”. We emphasize how the mistakes made and challenges experienced have gradually helped shape the current objectives of this project. The project started in 2016 with the aim of measuring the home range of birds in a forest remnant with the help of the public. Each bird was banded with a unique combination of colors, and the public was recruited to visit the site. Upon resighting a banded bird, the participants were encouraged to report the exact location of the encounter, time, date, and band color combination. In the first attempt, the low number of citizens engaged (n=10) was insufficient to collect the data necessary to investigate forest species. However, the same monitoring method was opportunely tested in subsequent studies that required information on individual birds. Driven by the curiosity of several citizens, we studied Red-legged Seriema and Southern House Wren behavior in urban landscapes, and the effects of feeders on bird communities. Even with a small team with high turnover, limited funding, and technological limitations, from 2016 to 2023, the project banded 515 birds of 94 species at seven locations and generated 986 resighting records with the contribution of 329 citizens. These results and the success of the investigations have determined the project’s future scope of activities. We hope that the trajectory of the project expressed in this manuscript inspires other Brazilians to overcome possible challenges when implementing their citizen science projects.

Keywords: animal behavior; bird banding; bird feeders; birdwatching; ecotourism; ornithology

1. Contextualization

Citizen science is a scientific approach that has gained significant attention in Brazil over the past 10 years, within educational and research institutions, as well as among public authorities and society (Cunha et al. 2017, Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023). The definition of citizen science depends on the context (Haklay et al. 2021), but in ecological and ornithological projects, a conservative and illustrative way to understand it is to consider it as "the participation of non-professionals in genuine scientific investigations". The form of participation can vary in intensity and frequency across different stages of the scientific project (Shirk et al. 2012, Haklay et al. 2021). Although this scientific approach is promising worldwide, planning and acquiring financial support and the material means to conduct a citizen science project is not trivial. In Brazil, particularly within ecological or ornithological based research, there are still few projects reporting mistakes, successes, and adjustments made throughout the project lifetime (e.g., Alexandrino et al. 2019a, Comandulli and Alexandrino 2021). The lack of experience reports in Brazilian literature leaves various enthusiasts of the participatory knowledge-building process without examples to follow or avoid (Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023).

Therefore, in this manuscript, we present the experiences of the “Did I see a banded bird!?”. project (“*Eu vi uma ave usando pulseiras!*”, original name in Portuguese) from 2016 to 2023, highlighting how citizens helped in conducting different scientific investigations, some of which were unexpected, and how the ‘project team – participants’ interactions shaped the project's overall

structure and objectives. We present a compilation of different events that occurred during the three phases of the project, from its inception to the current phase. The manuscript brings reports from published studies, but we also present unpublished data.

2. Results achieved and lessons learned

2.1. Phase 1 – First attempts and adjustments (October 2016 to October 2019)

The project started in October 2016, based at the *Laboratório de Ecologia Manejo e Conservação da Fauna Silvestre, do departamento de Ciências Florestais da Escola Superior de Agricultura “Luiz de Queiroz”, Universidade de São Paulo (LEMAC/LCF/ESALQ/USP)*. It was created as an auxiliary method to monitor the home range of birds in a forest remnant surrounded by sugarcane plantations in the rural district of Santa Olímpia, municipality of Piracicaba/SP. The project's goal was to measure the potential of common forest species in promoting forest restoration (Alexandrino et al. 2019a). In the remnant, each captured bird received up to three colored bands in a distinct sequence and a metal band with a unique number from the *Centro Nacional de Pesquisa e Conservação de Aves Silvestres - CEMAVE* (Banding Authorization - CEMAVE Project No. 4141, SISBIO License No. 5503). The colored bands allowed the resighting and identification of each bird from a distance, enabling the recording of its occurrence at different locations in the forest. Citizen recruitment occurred between April 2017 and April 2018, targeting nature enthusiasts, including birdwatchers of various experience levels. Every user of the WikiAves platform living in the state of São Paulo received an invitation message, along with short messages and explanatory videos about the project. We also posted the same invitation message in different Facebook communities. Lectures and word-of-mouth promotion at bird fairs and events attended by Brazilian birdwatchers were also used during the recruitment phase. Citizens were invited to visit the forest remnant for a morning of birding and to help look for banded birds. Once found, we asked observers to report the date, time, location of observation, species, and the colors of each band. By May 2018, 302 people had expressed their intention to participate in the project by responding to a short questionnaire (Certificate of Presentation of Ethical Appreciation at ESALQ/USP - CAEE No. 63717316.5.0000.5395), with several indicating a high propensity to visit the site (e.g., 155 lived within 200 km of the site, and at least 64 people declared they would travel this distance to participate in the project, see Alexandrino et al. 2019a).

2.1.1 First failures observed – Engaging citizens is not that simple

In the beginning, the number of people interested in participating in the project seemed high (i.e., 302 people), but within a year (April 2017 - April 2018), only 10 people visited the forest remnant we were monitoring, and each person only once. These numbers were far below the expected participation level and what was necessary to achieve the intended scientific research, especially considering that 64 people who lived near the study site had declared a high likelihood of visiting it. We observed that various factors contributed to this lack of success, ranging from the inability to ensure minimum safety for volunteers visiting the site to the absence of a community of species that were naturally attractive to most birdwatchers, such as endemic and endangered species (Alexandrino et al. 2019a, Comandulli and Alexandrino 2021). Volunteers who visited the site also complained about the difficulty in following the data collection protocol

due to the natural challenge of spotting birds in the forest environment (i.e., low visual detection and predominance of auditory detection).

The method of submitting records was informal, involving filling out a spreadsheet sent by the project coordinator or using a simple app for submitting records, both of which prevented the participating citizens from learning (see challenges section). As a result, two basic principles of citizen science were not being respected (e.g., principles: "Citizen science provides benefits to both science and society" and "Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project"; RBCC 2023). Much of this stemmed from the project coordinator's limited understanding of citizen science at the time, which focused on recruiting citizens to collect data for formal researchers during their leisure activities (i.e., a view solely aligned with Bonney 1996). A wide range of factors that could determine citizen engagement in scientific projects were not being considered (Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023). These shortcomings caused the few participants to fail to promote the project positively. By mid-2018, when the severity of these failures was recognized, it was impossible to reverse the situation, as there were no funds available to implement adjustments.

2.1.2 Second attempt – Correcting the first failures

Although the first attempt of the project was unsuccessful, its innovative nature caught the attention of the Brazilian public. Notably, 94 citizens who filled out the participation form for the project's first attempt lived more than 300 km from the project site. Additionally, messages with photos of banded birds from other parts of Brazil, along with questions about the bird's origin, began to be sent to the project (e.g., Ribeiro et al. 2022). These facts indicated that monitoring banded birds with citizen support could be promising, prompting the coordinator to test out the project a second time, addressing the shortcomings identified in the first attempt.

In early November 2018, the project opportunistically tested the same monitoring methodology with a juvenile Red-legged Seriema (*Cariama cristata*, a large terrestrial bird that was approximately 30 days old) on the "Luiz de Queiroz" university campus in Piracicaba/SP. The initial idea was to track the locations frequented by this individual and their family (one adult and another juvenile) on the campus and their habitat preferences (the campus covered 914.5 ha and included urban, rural, and forested areas). The public was recruited through Facebook, a social network widely used at the time, and the submission of records for the banded seriema was centralized in the group "Did you see a seriema at ESALQ?"¹. Between November 5, 2018, when the juvenile was banded, and August 9, 2019, the date of its last sighting, 668 records of seriemas were obtained on the campus (an average of 3 records per day, with 529 of the banded seriema alone). Even after the disappearance of the banded seriema, for unknown reasons, and the consequent end of monitoring, the project still received 96 additional records of unbanded seriemas seen on the campus until February 27, 2020, demonstrating the popularity of this monitoring effort. In the end, 188 citizens participated in the monitoring, including students, staff, and visitors of ESALQ. Scientifically, the monitoring identified threats faced by the Seriemas on the campus and recognized the lack of adaptive behaviors in the juveniles for surviving in an urban environment (Alexandrino et al. 2019b).

A combination of factors explains the success of the seriema monitoring and was discussed in detail in Comandulli and Alexandrino (2021). For the present manuscript, it is important to highlight that the participants' curiosity about different observed behaviors of the seriemas guided

¹ The Facebook group's original name in Portuguese was "Você viu uma seriema na ESALQ?".
<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1947269508912397>

the project team to conduct a scientific investigation different from what was initially planned. Initially, we only expected citizens to provide spatial records of seriemas (i.e., where they were sighted). However, over time, people began sending photos and videos along with their reports, revealing some of the birds' behaviors. This fact allowed us to investigate the behaviors they exhibit to survive in an urbanized area with high human activity, cars, and hundreds of abandoned domestic cats (Alexandrino et al. 2019b). Because of this new research, more people felt motivated to help with the monitoring, and ultimately propose decision-making based on the obtained results (e.g., installing street signs about driving carefully on campus, not feeding wild animals, etc., Comandulli and Alexandrino 2021). The key lesson from this first successful experience was that the relationship between the project team and the citizens needs to go beyond requesting data collection (e.g., providing updates on monitoring results and listening to citizens when they show interest in other investigative stages).

2.2 Phase 2 - Project expansion (October 2019 – March 2020)

The second half of 2019 marked the beginning of the project's expansion to other parts of Brazil. Encouraged by the successful monitoring of seriemas on the "Luiz de Queiroz" campus, we wondered what other research contexts, environments, audiences, and bird species the project could be applied to. In October 2019, the project was implemented in the region of the urban park 'Museu de Biologia Prof. Mello Leitão – MBML' (which houses the National Institute of the Atlantic Forest), in the Santa Teresa/ES municipality, and in the urban park 'Mini-Horto' of Águas de São Pedro/SP. Between November 2019 and March 2020, the project was also established at 'Fazenda Elguero/RPPN Trápaga', a rural/forest landscape in São Miguel Arcanjo/SP, and in the private forest reserve 'Legado das Águas', in Miracatu/SP (Figure 1). Both sites were studied by the project coordinator's master's student (see Alcantara 2022). Banding was one of the methods used in Alcantara's master's project to mark birds and monitor them at feeders using camera traps.

During the expansion period, we also decided to use Instagram (@aves.usando.pulseiras) and YouTube to help promote the project.

Figure 1. (A) Locations where the project ‘Did I see a banded bird!?’ has been implemented (State of São Paulo and Espírito Santo are marked in red): 1 – Santa Olímpia Rural district, 2 – “Luiz de Queiroz” campus (both in Piracicaba/SP); 3 – Mini Horto of Águas de São Pedro/SP; 4 – Fazenda Elguero/RPPN Trápaga (São Miguel Arcanjo/SP); 5 – Reserva Legado das Águas (Miracatu/SP); 6 – Urban park Museu de Biologia Prof. Mello Leitão – MBML, 7 – Pousada Sitio Canaã (both in Santa Teresa/ES); NOTE: The Aves de Noronha project is conducting tests on the island of Fernando de Noronha, and therefore the island is listed here as location 8. Locations marked with * have bird feeders under monitoring; (B) Number of banded bird records provided by citizens, without the presence of the project team. At Fazenda Elguero/RPPN Trápaga, there were only records made when the project team was conducting bird observation with citizens. (C) Number of banded bird records provided by citizens in each study area.

2.3 After 2020 – Focusing on new opportunities and defining the project's future

In March 2020, the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic in Brazil interrupted visits to the four locations where the project was active. Although the number of banded bird sightings and public participation in monitoring were few during the first six months of the pandemic, this pause was an opportunity for the project team to review the data that had already been collected in the new locations and to evaluate the knowledge demands raised by the public up to that time. Then,

we decided to analyze an opportunistic monitoring effort initiated thanks to the curiosity of a citizen who reported Southern House Wrens (*Troglodytes musculus*, one of which was banded by the project) performing successive nesting attempts in his motorcycle helmet. The monitoring was conducted with the citizen's help in December 2019 at MBML using a camera trap placed in front of the helmet to discover the reasons for these nesting attempts. A scientific article co-authored by the helmet's owner was produced, presenting new evidence explaining how Southern House Wrens gain reproductive advantages by living in human-dominated environments (Alexandrino et al. 2022a).

Another opportunity identified in 2020 was the possibility of conducting scientific investigations with citizens about the impacts caused by bird feeders. During the project's expansion, a questionnaire was distributed to various birdwatchers in Brazil (Certificate of Presentation of Ethical Appreciation at ESALQ/USP - CAEE – No. 30778720.2.0000.5395, linked to Maristela C. Alcantara's master's project), which included a question reflecting the curiosity level of birdwatchers if they observed a banded bird at a feeder. From the 451 respondents, 373 (82%) indicated they would like to know why the bird was banded and its history. This result, combined with the increased interest of Brazilians in bird feeders during the pandemic (Alexandrino et al. 2022b), led the project to focus its efforts on; (1) encouraging citizens to record and report banded birds observed at feeders in some of the project's locations, and (2) inviting citizens to analyze videos from camera traps monitoring feeders (during citizen scientist training courses, an activity initiated in February 2023). With this approach, the project began to assess, together with citizens, the frequency of occurrence of each banded individual at the feeders (following what was carried out in Alcantara 2022), as well as quantify different behaviors exhibited by various species at these structures. Since 2021, several studies have been produced, focusing on indications of the positive and negative impacts caused by feeders (e.g., Rui et al. 2021, Alcantara and Alexandrino 2022).

2.4 General results – banded birds, reports, and public participation

In general, from the beginning of the project until the close of this manuscript (May 2023), considering all the locations where the project was installed and kept active (Figure 1a)², a total of 515 birds of 94 species have been banded, and 963 records of banded birds have been submitted by 271 citizens. An additional 75 records were made in the field by the project team in the company of 58 citizens (overall total – 986 records involving 329 citizens). During this period, we also conducted camera trapping at 21 feeders across five locations (Figure 1). Out of the 69,837 videos obtained, 22,740 have been analyzed. Birds were present in 32.5% of these videos, with banded birds appearing in 1,897 videos (8.3%). We had the assistance of 37 citizens in sorting these videos during the citizen scientist training courses. After the project's expansion, the number of participants varied across locations, with sites that had greater ecotourism incentives (e.g., Legado das Águas and MBML) having higher participant numbers and consequently more records of banded birds (Figures 1b and 1c).

2.5 Internal challenges faced

² The project also did bird banding at Pousada Sítio Canaã, in the rural area of Santa Teresa/ES municipality, but due to the Covid-19 pandemic, participatory monitoring was not implemented at the site. In 2020, the 'Aves de Noronha' project began tests to apply the project's methodology in monitoring some of the island's birds. Due to the lack of access to this project's data, the island of Fernando de Noronha was not considered in the results presented here. From 2021 onwards, new species have been banded on the "Luiz de Queiroz" campus for future research.

Every scientific project has problems along its path, including the "Did I see a banded bird!?" project. Here are some of the challenges that we need to share:

- *Organization of records and interaction with the public:* After 2019, due to the numerous banded birds to monitor and the various channels through which citizens can contact our project (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, email, etc.), we realized it would be difficult to keep up with the submission of records. Additionally, our interaction with citizens has become challenging. The non-centralized submission of records requires substantial effort from the project team to manually search for, save, and enter each record into the project's database. There is a need for automating the organization of banded bird reports and public interaction. However, current online tools useful for citizen science, like eBird, WikiAves, and iNaturalist, do not offer ideal functionalities (e.g., easy visualization of each bird's history when a citizen submits a record, visualization of preliminary results). Thus, the project attempted to develop its own app twice (in 2018 and 2023). Due to a lack of financial resources, neither version achieved excellence (i.e., the first only allowed data submission. The second version included the desired features previously mentioned, but its usability was not very attractive to the public, who consequently continued submitting records via social media).
- *Funding and team:* Firstly, it is important to note that due to the nature of the research being conducted by the project (non-threatened birds living near humans), access to funding has always been limited, relying mainly on the coordinator's funds. Although the project attempts to maintain partners in each location where it is established, support is usually limited to logistics, accommodations, and meals. Due to financial constraints and the inability to hire a professional or offer financial compensation, the project cannot maintain a stable, dedicated team for long periods, relying on undergraduate students volunteering their time.

Given the difficulties highlighted here, focusing on research opportunities that arise from the data produced has been a way to keep the project active and recognized by the public.

2.6 So, what is the “Did I see a banded bird!?” project?

After experiencing all the challenges and course adjustments detailed here, as well as focusing on research opportunities driven by participant curiosity, the project currently defines itself as a citizen science initiative that promotes the monitoring of various banded birds in different locations in the Atlantic Forest (whether anthropized or preserved zones) with the help of the public. Various research questions, embedded in diverse contexts that require data on individual birds, are explored in each location where the project is implemented. However, the core principle and ultimate objective remain consistent: engaging citizens to report their sightings of banded birds so that they gain environmental and scientific awareness as they participate in research (e.g., understanding the impacts of anthropogenic activities on birds; learning how scientific investigations are conducted). Additionally, the project helps to promote the culture of banded bird monitoring in the country. Many Brazilians still do not understand the reasons for banding wild birds and the entire process involved (e.g., who can band them, necessary licenses, objectives, etc.), and there are misconceptions among Brazilians that every banded bird belongs to someone and consequently has some financial value (Costa and Monteiro 2016, Ribeiro et al. 2022).

Currently, the project aligns with a broader vision of citizen science, as suggested by the Brazilian Citizen Science Network (RBCC 2023), no longer limiting citizens to data collection (see Alexandrino 2023, www.avesusandopulseiras.com.br). We recognize that each scientific investigation we conduct may require different types of interactions between citizens and the project team. Our research can be initiated by both the project team (e.g., Alexandrino et al. 2019b, Ribeiro et al. 2022) and citizens (e.g., Alexandrino et al. 2022a). We hope that these decisions will help the project remain active in the years following this publication.

Finally, we demonstrate that diverse and unexpected challenges can arise in a citizen science project, but they do not necessarily determine its failure. We show that taking the time to listen to the citizens who contact the project team can create future opportunities. We hope that the story of our project so far will inspire other Brazilians to overcome potential challenges when executing their own citizen science projects.

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